

INCEPTION MEETING REPORT

Held September 6-8, 2023 in Kampala, Uganda (and on Zoom)

Links:

[Full meeting agenda](#)
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THE RTB BREEDING INVESTMENT

Root, Tuber, and Banana (RTB) crops are vital for combatting poverty, enhancing food security, and building climate-resilient agriculture in Africa, benefiting smallholder farmers. Science-based plant breeding plays a crucial role in this endeavor, emphasizing market-driven approaches and continuous modernization to boost genetic gains and accelerate the adoption of innovative crop varieties. Supported by the Bill and Melinda Gates Foundation (BMGF), RTB Breeding focuses on integrating modern breeding techniques, fostering collaborations between CGIAR and NARS, and adopting a holistic, cross-cutting approach to benefit end-users, particularly farmers.

THE KICK-OFF MEETING

The RTB kick-off meeting promoted cross-learning, trust-building, and collaborative discussions, highlighting the significance of working together. The event provided valuable insights into the challenges and opportunities of banana, cassava, and sweetpotatoes teams, fostering a shared vision and commitment to delivering improved RTB crop varieties for African farmers and beneficiaries. RTB Breeding is poised to lead the transformation of Africa's agricultural landscape, one crop at a time.

MEETING STATS

- **70+** in person participants from **24** partner organizations
- **55+** Zoom participants
- **29** presentations

SESSION 1: A HIGH-LEVEL, LONG TERM PERSPECTIVE ON RTB BREEDING

A senior representative from Uganda's Ministry of Agriculture, Dr. Yona Baguma, highlighted the significance of RTB Breeding for African smallholder farmers, and reminded the team that the farmer was the boss. Distinguished speakers, including Dr. Jim Lorenzen of the BMGF (pictured left) and Prof. Garba H. Sharubutu of ARCN, Nigeria, offered valuable insights into the role of RTB crops in Africa's development and poverty alleviation. Dr. Lorenzen reminded the team that RTB are adaptable to climate change with the ability to sustain. He mentioned that the team needs to deliver and show that RTB can be priority crops for funding.

Scarlett Crawford, presenting on behalf of Dr. Sonja Vermeulen (Managing Director of Genetic Innovation) showcased the pioneering example of funding breeding at CGIAR, and Dr. Simon Heck, Director General of CIP, discussed the role of RTB crops in African food systems.

KEY QUESTIONS FROM SESSION 1

1. How can we manage communication within the CGIAR structure to ensure that all stakeholders are informed?
2. What are the major drivers of consumer preference in Africa, beyond consumer traits, such as policy, processing, transportation, and credit agencies?
3. How does the project address gender issues, and in what specific ways?

SESSIONS 2 & 3: NUTS AND BOLTS , WORKING AS A HIGH-PERFORMING TEAM

Session 2 included presentations from all the crop leads, as well as the leads from the gender and quality teams. We got into the nuts and bolts of breeding banana, cassava, potato, sweetpotato, and yam. Each presenter gave an overview of their respective former projects, emphasizing progress, approaches, expected genetic gains, key traits, deliverables, countries served, and partnerships. This session facilitated a comprehensive understanding of breeding progress in RTB crops.

In session 3, Richard Ofei explained the Project Management Unit's (PMU) role in supporting the delivery of project results, including financial reporting, M&E, communication, and contracts. There were several questions and suggestions during the Q&A sessions.

Rony Sweenen raised concerns about terminology differences between primary outcomes, intermediate outcomes, and outputs, suggesting the need for an ontology of the system. Carlos Iglesias pointed out the absence of representation from NARES in the PMU, and Richard mentioned they would consider it. The structure of budget allocation and reporting to stakeholders was discussed, emphasizing the need for effective communication.

Dominique Dufour highlighted the importance of science and impact-oriented reporting. Craig Yencho emphasized the need for regular communication and interaction on scientific matters. NARO raised concerns about reporting arrangements, customization of the platform, and the specific guidelines for reporting.

Chiedozie Egesi clarified the role of the PMU as a service unit and the decision-making power at the crop lead and local PI levels. Priver Namanya Bwesigze called for a clearer administrative and management structure. Garba Sharubutu questioned the participation of government institutions as partners.

The discussion concluded with plans for a more detailed management structure discussion and two types of platforms for reporting: PMC for technical reporting by partners and PRMS for reporting in the technical arrangement format for One CG once deliverables are uploaded in the PMC.

KEY TAKEAWAYS/NEXT STEPS FROM PMU DISCUSSION

- **Emphasis on Communication and Collaboration:** Effective communication and collaboration are emphasized throughout the discussions. There is a clear need for better communication both within the project team and with external stakeholders, including NARES (National Agricultural Research Systems). Regular communication, webinars, and annual meetings are planned to ensure effective dissemination of project progress and results.
- **Reporting Arrangements:** Several partners raised concerns about reporting arrangements and the need for customization. The PMU needs to hold some more training meetings and further clarify the reporting structure. Clear schedules for reporting also need to be established.
- **Management Structure:** Several participants expressed concerns about the project's management structure, emphasizing the need for clarity and improved coordination. The suggestion of establishing an Advisory Committee to connect donors, CGIAR, CG partners, NARES, and regional bodies is under consideration. Clarity on the roles of different entities, including the PMU and crop leads, is essential for efficient project management. Further discussions and clarity regarding the management structure are expected in the coming weeks.

SESSION 4: WORK PLANNING

In this session, crop teams formed breakout groups to work on reviewing the results framework for the project, and define activities for the investment period. Here, Dr. Maria Andrade leads the sweetpotato team through the session.

SESSION 5: INTERACTIONS BETWEEN RTB AND GENETIC INNOVATION

This session featured talks by Dr. John Derera and Dr. Michael Quinn, shedding light on the context of RTB Breeding within the realm of Genetic Innovation and fostering collaborations between Accelerated Breeding and RTB Breeding.

Dr. Julius Okello discussed interactions between market intelligence initiative (MIPPI) and RTB Breeding, while Dr. Dorcus Gemenet delved into genetic gains assessments in RTB crops in the light of accelerated breeding Initiative (ABI.)

SESSION 6: NARS VIEWS ON BREEDING NETWORKS, DATABASES, QUALITY SELECTION, AND PROSSIVA

Dr. Priver Namanya, Dr. Moses Nyongesa, and Dr. Jude Obidiedwu shared expectations and concerns from National Programs about CGIAR-NARS breeding networks, providing valuable insights into a meaningful collaborative CG-NARS landscape.

Dr. Lukas Mueller discussed the development of RTB databases, while Dr. Dominique Dufour and Dr. Delphine Amah presented on selecting elite RTB crops breeding lines and linking RTB Breeding Genetic Gains with accelerated variety adoption through PROSSIVA. The session also included a World Café discussion on gender and quality, hosted by Dr. Dominique Dufour and Dr. Béla Teeken.

KEY TAKEAWAYS FROM SESSIONS 5 & 6:

The discussion centered on transitioning from BreedBase to EBS raised concerns about user comfort and emphasized the importance of involving users in the transition process to avoid loss of utility and resources accrued in BreedBase. It was suggested that research teams should be informed of any potential issues with using the current databases. Additionally, discussions are ongoing regarding desired improvements and standardization of databases, with a plan to engage research teams in the decision-making process. Meanwhile, the recommendation was to allow breeders and research teams to continue using BreedBase. The need for a participatory and consultative approach to critical decisions impacting users was stressed. In another topic, there was a call for further discussion to clarify the CG-NARS partnership. Finally, the difference between Demand Creation Trials and Product Launch Trials was explained, with the former focused on creating demand for new products and the latter aimed at demonstrating new products. Craig commented on the potential of PROSSIVA to support strategies for product scaling and addressing challenges in vegetative propagation.

Grace Wamue speaking during a panel on gender and quality traits, led by Béla Teeken and Tessy Madu.

SESSION 7: RTB CROPS CGIAR-NARS BREEDING NETWORKS

Dr. Bish Das and others explored how to build sustainable CGIAR-NARS breeding networks in RTB crops, drawing lessons from Musa and potato examples. The importance and expectations of such breeding networks were made clear. Point people were assigned for each crop/team to continue working on shaping these networks, in collaboration with Bish.

Subsequently, a discussion led by Dr. David Meyer, Dr. Steve Rounsley, and Dr. Carlos Iglesias delved into the shift from an individual crop to a RTB crops mindset, drawing lessons from industry success and pitfalls in large-scale breeding across diverse crops. (A slide from their presentation is shown below.)

The RTB group should unite around the opportunities ahead

<p>Crop characteristics</p>	<p>Resiliency against climate change</p>	<p>Technology opportunities</p>
<p>Systems approach</p>		
<p>Income generation</p>	<p>Gender equality</p>	<p>Demographic effect on food production/consumption</p>

FIELD VISIT TO RESEARCH FACILITIES IN NAMULONGE AND SENDUSU

Participants embarked on an insightful field visit to the research facilities in Namulonge and Sendusu. The day began with an address by the NaCRRRI Director at NaCRRRI, setting the tone for the visit. The program included lab visits at NaCRRRI and the rest of the day's activities split into two groups, where Group A explored IITA-NARL Banana and IITA Cassava at Sendusu, while Group B toured NaCRRRI Screenhouses, NaCRRRI Cassava, and CIP Sweetpotato at Namulonge. This provided participants with a firsthand look at the ongoing research and breeding efforts for these important RTB crops.

The visit concluded with a lunch and final address at NaCRRRI, featuring remarks from key institutional representatives including key persons at NARO-NaCRRRI (Esuma and Titus) CIP Country Representative - Uganda, Project EPAC members - (Carlos) and other speakers. Special recognition to RTB project managers, principal investigators were also made. It was a day of hands-on learning and valuable insights into the research and breeding activities conducted at these research facilities, further enhancing the understanding of RTB Breeding efforts.

RTB BREEDING PARTNERS